

CRITERIA FOR EDUCATING THE YOUNGER GENERATION IN THE SPIRIT OF PATRIOTISM

Axmadaliyev Elmurod Raxmatovich

Bukhara Innovation University

70110103- 2nd cycle Master's degree in Educational Institution Management.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15160989>

Abstract. *This article provides feedback on the criteria and principles of educating the younger generation in the spirit of patriotism.*

Keywords: *patriotism, world, nation, noble thought, justice, criterion.*

Аннотация. *В статье дается обратная связь по критериям и принципам воспитания подрастающего поколения в духе патриотизма.*

Ключевые слова: *патриотизм, мир, нация, благородная мысль, справедливость, критерий.*

In the context of the construction of New Uzbekistan, the creation of the foundation of the third Renaissance and based on the Uzbekistan 2030 Strategy [2], the state and society are faced with important tasks to reform all aspects of people's lives. An important place in this series is occupied by the issues of spiritual and moral education of the younger generation, among which patriotic education stands out. As the President of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev notes: «... in the conditions of globalization and the growing struggle for the minds and hearts of people, especially the younger generation, the role and importance of military-patriotic education is increasing.

Today, each of us must be a true patriot of the Motherland and educate our youth in this spirit.»[1] Patriotism is a moral principle, one of the deepest feelings formed over thousands of years in the national traditions of the Uzbek people. This is devotion to one's people, love for the nature of one's native land, respect for culture and objects of art, recognized as the invaluable heritage of humanity. The President of the country notes: «...everyone knows that patriotism is the moral basis for the viability of any state and acts as an important mobilizing resource for the comprehensive development of society.» [3] According to the leader of the country, the idea of forming a state with a great future can only be achieved by a strong young generation, brought up in the spirit of high moral qualities and deep patriotism. In achieving this historical task lies an internal source of high morale - the national idea.

The great Uzbek thinker A. Navoi in his works attached great importance to the problems of educating the younger generation in the spirit of deep patriotism.

He also wrote about family education, because... It is precisely this that lays the foundations of intelligence, moral and physical health, which are the foundation of patriotism. One can give many striking examples of true devotion and patriotism towards one's Motherland. For example, Jaloliddin Manguberdi, who fought for the independence of his people and region during the conquests of Genghis Khan. The purpose of patriotic education is to form persistent, conscious, convinced patriots, devoted to the ideals of national independence, distinguished by high intellectual, mental, physical and combat qualities necessary for the defense of the state. Under these conditions, the establishment in the public consciousness of the people, and especially the younger generation, of the idea of deep patriotism, pride in their Motherland, and readiness to defend it has been and remains one of the most important tasks of high spirituality of society and a priority of state policy. Patriotic education is closely related to other areas of education, but the specificity of its goals and objectives makes it an independent direction in the general process of spiritual education. Patriotic education in multinational Uzbekistan helps to strengthen unity and solidarity, including among different ethnic and sociocultural groups represented in the country.

This helps overcome differences and avoid conflict, creating the basis for a peaceful and prosperous society. The role of the state in nurturing deep love for the Motherland cannot be overestimated, and therefore today we are observing historical processes in this direction.

The main idea of the events being held is «From national revival to national progress.» The initiatives currently being implemented for the patriotic education of the younger generation can be divided into several groups, each of which is undergoing in-depth work. 1. Updating the educational system. Materials dedicated to Russian history, culture and traditions are integrated into the curriculum. This helps youth develop a deep respect for their country and its heritage. 2. Carrying out patriotic events. Educational institutions hold events dedicated to historical dates and events, national holidays and achievements of Uzbekistan. This allows young people to better understand and appreciate their homeland. 3. Creation of youth organizations. It is important to support and develop volunteer and youth organizations that are involved in improving public places, helping those in need and other social projects. This contributes to the formation of an active citizenship position and a sense of responsibility to society. 4. Support for youth initiatives.

Conducting competitions, issuing grants and other programs to support innovative ideas and projects created by the new generation.

This stimulates the development of the creative potential of young people and promotes the growth of patriotism through active participation in public life. 5. Use of modern technologies and mass media.

Young people are actively involved through social networks, online platforms and other means of communication in order to disseminate patriotic ideas, information about national culture and history. In the age of modern technology, this is what allows us to achieve greater audience coverage and establish mutual contact with young people. The family plays a major role in instilling a patriotic spirit in the younger generation. In traditional Uzbek culture, each cell of society is an integral part of the institution of socialization, the basis of which is spiritual values, national traditions and respect for the native land, passed on from generation to generation. Parents and older relatives tell children about important events in the history of the country, its achievements and cultural heritage. Family holidays and traditions are also important in the formation of patriotic feelings and cultural values. At the state level, a number of legislative acts related to the patriotic education of the younger generation have been adopted in Uzbekistan. Thus, on June 29, 2023, Cabinet of Ministers Resolution No. 267 «On measures to increase the efficiency of work on military-patriotic education of youth» was adopted. [4] This document approves the Concept for increasing the effectiveness of work on military-patriotic education of youth for 2023–2027. The country has decided that from the beginning of the 2024-2025 academic year, the educational system of the republic plans to create specialized militarypatriotic classes in each school. The main goal of this project is to educate the younger generation in the spirit of patriotism and readiness to defend the Motherland. In such classes, they will actively promote the activities of the military-patriotic movement «Vatan Ugloni» (Hero of the Motherland), which was created in 2021 at the initiative of the President with the aim of introducing the principle of patriotism into the educational process and educating citizens with a sense of love and devotion to their country.

Thus, it can be emphasized that the activities of the state and society for the patriotic education of youth in conditions of independence are an urgent need and require further development and improvement.

REFERENCES

1. Камилова, Г. А., Курбанова, Г. Р., & Джаббарова, С. З. (2020). Особенности формирования педагогических навыков у воспитателей дошкольно-образовательных учреждений. *Academy*, (5 (56)), 25-27.
2. Камилова, Г. А., & Тураева, О. С. К. (2021). ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ДИАГНОСТИЧЕСКИХ НАВЫКОВ У СТУДЕНТОВ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ. *Проблемы науки*, (4 (63)), 50-52.

3. Камилова, Г. А., & Курбонова, Г. Р. (2020). Эффективность экологического образования: образование дошкольников с помощью педагогических технологий. *Academy*, (12 (63)), 60-62.
4. Камилова, Г. А., & Курбонова, Г. Р. (2020). ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ: ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ С ПОМОЩЬЮ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ. *Academy*, (12), 60-62.
5. Камилова, Г. А. (2021). Развитие системы дошкольного образования. *Вестник науки и образования*, (16-2 (119)), 86-88.
6. Alimovna, K. G. (2022). Laws of Ecological Education. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 2(2), 241-244.
7. KAMILOVA, G. (2024). EKOLOGIK TARBIYADA PAREMIOLOGIYA VA UNING XUSUSIYATLARI. *News of the NUUz*, 1(1.1), 83-86.
8. Kamilova, G. A. (2024). PARAMERIK JANRLAR VOSITASIDA EKOLOGIK MADANIYATNI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA PSIXOLOGIK YONDASHUV. *Inter education & global study*, (5), 565-5574.
9. Камилова, Г. А. (2023). Мактабгача Таълим Ташкилотларида Экологик Тарбия. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 42, 330-333.
10. Kamilova, G. A., & Rozieva, Z. E. (2022). Botirova. *Ню А. Мактабгача таълим ташкилотларида болаларни экологик-гигиенлик тарбиялаш имкониятлари. Мактабгача таълим-Мактаб-Олий таълим концепсияси муаммо, ечимлар ва истиқболлар халқаро илмий-амалий анжуман материаллари. Бухоро*, 46-48.
11. Kamilova, G. A., & Rozieva, Z. E. (2022). Botirova. *Ню А. Мактабгача таълим ташкилотларида болаларни экологик-гигиенлик тарбиялаш имкониятлари. Мактабгача таълим-Мактаб-Олий таълим концепсияси муаммо, ечимлар ва истиқболлар халқаро илмий-амалий анжуман материаллари. Бухоро*, 46-48.
12. Kamilova, G. (2020). Мактабгача таълим муассасаларида экологик тарбияни ташкил этишда интегратив йондашув. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz)*, 1(1).
13. Камилова, Г. А., & Нарзиева, Д. Б. (2022). Повышение экономической грамотности у детей дошкольного возраста с помощью развития коммуникативных компетенций. *Вестник науки и образования*, (8 (128)), 44-46.
14. Камилова, Г. А., & Нарзиева, Д. Б. (2022). КОММУНИКАТИВНЫЕ КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ И ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКАЯ ГРАМОТНОСТЬ. *Вестник науки и образования*, (8 (128)), 47-50.

15. Kamilova, G. A. Go'Zal Rajab Qizi Qurbonova (2021). *МАКТАБГАЧА ТА'ЛИМ ТASHKILOTIARIGA RAHBARLIK VA BOSHQARISHDA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUV. Scientific progress, 2(7), 1149-1153.*
16. Kamilova, G. A. (2021). МАКТАБГАЧА ТА'ЛИМ ТASHKILOTIARIGA RAHBARLIK VA BOSHQARISHDA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUV. *Scientific progress, 2(7), 1149-1153.*
17. Камилова, Г. А., Султонова, М. И., & Бобожонова, М. А. (2023). ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ НОВОЙ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ STEAM В ДОШКОЛЬНОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ. *Вестник науки и образования, (5 (136)-2), 41-44.*
18. Safarova, S., & Kamilova, G. (2024). МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARNING ERKIN FIKIRLASHINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA INTERFAOL USULLARNING ANAMIYATI. *Modern Science and Research, 3(12), 504-507.*
19. Камилова, Г. А., Мухаммедова, М. М., & Жабборова, О. С. К. (2023). МЕТОДИКА СИСТЕМАТИЧЕСКОГО ВКЛЮЧЕНИЯ МЕНТАЛЬНОЙ АРИФМЕТИКИ ЧЕРЕЗ ИГРЫ В ДОШКОЛЬНЫХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ. *Вестник науки и образования, (5 (136)-2), 38-41.*
20. Камилова, Г. А., & Кулиева, Х. Г. (2023). ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ МУЛЬТИМЕДИЙНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ДОШКОЛЬНЫХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ. *Вестник науки и образования, (4 (135)), 82-84.*
21. Jabbarov, I. A. U. (2022). TYPOLOGY AND FUNCTIONS OF A COMPLIMENT. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2(6), 854-860.*
22. Alimovna, K. G., & Abduraufovna, B. A. (2025). INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO CREATING A DEVELOPMENTAL ENVIRONMENT FOR PRESCHOOL CHILDREN. *Web of Teachers: Inderscience Research, 3(3), 1-5.*
23. Камилова, Г. А., & Тохирова, Ш. Б. К. (2023). ДИДАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ВТОРОМУ ЯЗЫКУ В РАЗВИТИИ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА ДЕТЕЙ В ДОШКОЛЬНЫХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЯХ. *Вестник науки и образования, (4 (135)), 84-88.*
24. Kamilova, G. A., & Jo'rayeva, D. R. (2022). Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni sifatli maktab ta'limiga tayyorlash imkoniyatlari,“. *Maktabgacha ta'lim-maktab-oliy ta'lim” konsepsiyasi: muammo, yechimlar va istiqbollar xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari.*
25. Rahmidinovna, Z. D. (2024). THE GOALS AND OBJECTIVES OF INTEGRATED CLASSES IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TECHNOLOGY CLASSES AND THE IMPORTANCE OF INTERDISCIPLINARY COMMUNICATION. *European International Journal of Pedagogics, 4(11), 50-55.*